

Munir's Model of Sustainable Education During the Uncertain Time

Note: This model was acknowledged and recognized by UNESCO during the World Higher Education Conference in 2021.

According to Munir, “The higher education sector has been on the brink of an epidemic, pandemic, and endemic crises. The sudden transition to remote learning during the recent uncertain time, for example, has aggravated educational poverty in some countries as a result of inadequate preparation, lack of ownership, and limited digital literacy.”

Munir proposes a sustainable education model using a participatory human-centered design approach. It begins with unearthing questions about sociocultural constraints, political situations, the availability of financial and human resources, and understanding the current state of social and educational policies and practices through multiple sources.

The next step is to identify risks and opportunities- assess the state of traditional and digital policies, and teaching and learning practices. This phase can be highly argumentative due to the absence of assessment mechanisms, potential ideological clashes, and backlash.

We need a customized plan of action and strategies that are contextually rooted. For this, it is crucial to involve community leaders, learners, and teachers throughout the process. By gathering narratives, we can establish a more comprehensive and effective educational plan.

Efforts should be made to promote conscious networking, digital literacy, and life skills. This should be done through an integrative, innovative, and inclusive approach, with a particular emphasis on supporting learners in taking ownership and developing resilience through personal identity exploration, subject to socio-cultural filtration. It is proposed to include courses on personal identity, digital literacy, future studies in education, human rights education, mental health education, and Open Educational Resources (OER), at the higher education level. To ensure equity and inclusion, it is important to adapt low-cost technologies and/or other asynchronous approaches to teaching and learning.

Throughout this model, interconnectedness, continuous reflection, risk management, quality participation, socio-emotional learning, mental hygiene, capacity building through self-empowerment skills, ethrical leadership, humanism, continuous learning, and amalgamation of peeragogy, cybergogy, and heutagogy must be taken on board.

- 0 Interconnectedness
- 0 Continuous Reflections
- 0 Risk Management
- 0 Quality participation
- 0 Social-emotional learning
- 0 Mental Hygiene
- 0 Capacity Building-Self-Empowerment Skills
- 0 Ethical Leadership
- 0 Humanism rather economic development
- 0 Continuous Learning
- 0 Pedagogies such as Rhizomatic

